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D17.1

Terms of Reference of the Communication Plan

Due date

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Terms of References of the Communication Plan

DELIVERABLE DESCRIPTION

This document outlines the communication strategy which NFFA-Europe Pilot will adopt, along with the related planned activities that will be carried out during the project lifetime, within task 17.1.1. "Communication plan definition".

Throughout the duration of the project, NFFA-Europe Pilot partners will concentrate their efforts on promoting the project among already established and potentially new groups of users, with the aim to raise awareness about NFFA-Europe infrastructures in general and in particular the new and more comprehensive research opportunities offered thanks to NFFA-Europe Pilot.

The communication plan provides a list of these activities, including press releases, the communication of project concepts, communication activities online and via social media, as well as a reference table that explains how activities are related to each other. Throughout the duration of the project, the effectiveness of communication initiatives will be assessed by using an ad-hoc monitoring system; the plan also presents this tool and key performance indicators that will be adopted.

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NATURE

R – Report

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

- P - Public
- PP - Restricted to other programme participants & EC: (Specify)
- RE - Restricted to a group (Specify)
- CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium

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INTRODUCTION

This Communication Plan sets the communication framework for the NFFA-Europe infrastructure and the related H2020 Pilot project. It serves as a guide for all communication activities throughout the project lifetime. This is a working document and will be updated as communication needs change, based on a process that will be finetuned throughout the project lifetime and entails: 1) identifying/updating specific communication objectives; 2) understanding the target audience; 3) developing messaging strategies; 4) selecting appropriate channels/tools; 5) disseminating messages through appropriate channels; and 6) conducting systematic research to inform and evaluate communication activities.

NFFA-Europe and Pilot in a nutshell

NFFA (Nanoscience foundries and fine analysis) represents an innovative research model for advanced nanofabrication and characterization of nanostructures. NFFA-Europe is a distributed, interoperable research infrastructure, implementing the NFFA model Europe-wide and offering its users the widest possible range of tools to carry out research at the nanoscale. NFFA-Europe Pilot is the new project financed by the European Commission offering yet more advanced facilities specialized on growth, nano-lithography, nano-characterization, theory and simulation. NFFA-Europe Pilot rests on three fundamental pillars:

- offering the facilities of the infrastructure free of charge to European and international users
- developing new services to improve interoperability
- developing new techniques to improve the offer

Outputs

Expected project **outputs** include the following:

- Scientific publications and data made available through FAIR data management;
- New patents originating from NFFA-Europe Pilot research projects;
- Training and educational activities;
- E-learning and digital schools on demand;
- NEP staff exchanges;
- Extension of the offer to new user groups;
- New techniques to amplify the offer;
- Innovative services of interoperability

Outcomes

To create a sustainable, long-term research infrastructure and to train a new generation of researchers in formulating their science objectives and research work-programmes by taking full advantage of this interoperable research infrastructure, so as to enhance European competitiveness in nanoscience and nano-to-micro analysis as well as nanotechnology.

Consortium

The NFFA-Europe Pilot Consortium consists of 22 partners from 11 European countries and is built around a core of European nanofoundries co-located with Analytical Large-Scale Facilities, including international organizations, university laboratories and two SMEs specialized in e-data and communication services. NFFA-Europe Infrastructure users have access to more than 180 techniques to carry out their research in the nanosciences and nanotechnologies.

COMMUNICATION PLAN

Communication goals and objectives

The aim of NFFA-Europe Pilot is to expand and consolidate the operation of an Interoperable Distributed Research Infrastructure for Nanoscience supporting research on materials and functional systems at the nano and at the microscale. To achieve this, NFFA-Europe Pilot is developing a series of new services and techniques, aiming to amplify and diversify its user network and hence the quality of its research outcomes.

The communication efforts will revolve around these activities with the purpose to:

- promote awareness of and excitement for the project among various research and scientific communities, different stakeholder groups including industrial realities as well as the general public;
- inform about the project, its opportunities, expected results and impacts, progresses and achievements;
- advertise and promote project events with the aim to engage stakeholders and users from established and new scientific fields (workshops, seminars, training sessions, webinars, staff exchanges, others);
- promote in particular the new installation offered, “nano to micro/macro” which takes the project out of the nano lot and into the micro and macro domains, making the entire research infrastructure appealing to new users;
- support stakeholder engagement so as to create links among external groups and the project team, through for example specific calls for industrial partners to join the consortium or to become a stakeholder linking the infrastructure with the innovation sector
- raise awareness among users and providers about the advantages that open science and open data can bring to the scientific community; promote FAIR principles and the data management tools provided by NFFA

NFFA-Europe Pilot communication will mainly focus on:

- project concepts and approaches
 - NFFA-Europe as a distributed research infrastructure that integrates nanofoundries (synthesis and manipulation of nanostructures) with fine analysis (nanocharacterization) theory and simulation tools available at European large-scale facilities.

- NFFA-Europe Pilot as the new project financed by the European Commission through its Horizon 2020 initiative, aiming to expand and consolidate the operation of an Interoperable Distributed Research Infrastructure for nanoscience and technology.
- The entire research offer can be accessed by submitting a single research proposal through a single-entry point on the NFFA.eu website.
- The research offer is free of charge for approved users.
- The offer is open to EU and international users.
- project events;
- achievements (e.g., success stories of outstanding research);
- training and educational activities.

Target audiences

A variety of actors may be interested in the research infrastructure offered through NFFA-Europe Pilot. As of today, identified target audiences include but are not limited to the following groups:

- scientific community at large and scientific societies in the fields of interest of NFFA-Europe Pilot:
 - Physics
 - Engineering
 - Materials sciences
 - Microelectronics
 - (Nano)Chemistry
 - Nanosafety
- Potential new users of the infrastructure in the fields of
 - Cultural Heritage
 - Archaeology
 - Life-sciences
 - Biotechnology
 - Energy
- similar existing initiatives and other research infrastructure organizations
- industrial sectors

A systematic understanding of the target groups' communication needs will enhance both communication efficiency and effectiveness. Supported by all project partners, Promoscience will carry out specific research to assess the users' current knowledge, attitudes, and communication preferences. According to the outcome of this research, specific communication objectives will be identified and adequate messaging strategies developed.

In a few cases, project communication activities will target the general public indiscriminately. However, the majority of campaigns (e.g. the specific campaign to inform past and potentially new researchers about the opening of new calls) will be directed towards specific groups, positioning the project in direct relation to the value and benefit existing or new users may obtain from the project. For each target group the research aims, ambitions, needs, scientific knowledge and experience in nanoscience will be taken into account when formulating the communication strategy. For example, when targeting the microelectronic device community, particular attention will be paid to the new installation “nano to micro/macro” when formulating the message.

A database of stakeholders and target groups will be established with the contribution of all partners in the docshare section of the project intranet based on Next Cloud, partners will be asked to provide stakeholder information according to the possible specific interests each of the indicated contacts may have towards the project (possible competitor, supporter/collaborator, potential user, other). The list will be reviewed and organised in order to segment stakeholders into a series of categories. The aim of this tool is to create a reference base to analyse the target audience and to facilitate communication efforts among partners, selected stakeholders and the identified target groups (e.g., to inform about upcoming events, or project activities and affairs). For the efficient implementation of this database, all partners will contribute by identifying and providing details about stakeholders and target groups of their local and international networks.

The template form to collect information is provided as Annex I to this communications plan.

Message strategies

For a more effective impact of the communication effort, key messages will be developed serving as a *fil rouge* in all kinds of project communications. These messages may be updated during the project lifetime according to the project progress and the results of the target audience analysis.

Agreed-upon key messages during the initial phase of the project include the following:

- NFFA-Europe is a distributed research infrastructure integrating nanofoundries (synthesis and manipulation of nanostructures) with fine analysis available at European large-scale facilities. It offers users the possibility to carry out cutting edge research at the frontier of the nanosciences and technologies with the widest range of tools for research at the nanoscale.
- Thanks to NFFA-Europe Pilot and the support of the European Commission, a more comprehensive catalogue of facilities and services can be offered to users for free.
- NFFA-Europe Pilot expands and consolidates the operation of an Interoperable Distributed Research Infrastructure for Nanoscience (IDRIN) – a unique platform to perform complex user projects, offering a seamless series of science services. NFFA-Europe Pilot is characterised by:
 - **Optimal integration** of the infrastructure services at the research level, by improving the combined access to a broad catalogue of state-of-the-art and unique facilities.
 - **Interoperability** at the data production and exploitation levels as a roadmap towards a new model of research infrastructure based on the creation of FAIR by-design datasets and the development of data analysis services.
 - **A new generation of researchers** trained to formulate their science objectives and research work programmes by taking full advantage of the interoperable research infrastructures of Europe.

- **Long-term sustainability** through optimization of good practices and investment by the Consortium members contributing to the co-creation process of Horizon Europe (HE) strategies and programmes.
- Access to these research facilities is free of charge.
- Comprehensive research plans can be communicated by means of a single proposal that is submitted through a single-entry point.
- Support by a team of experts to help frame the project in the preparation phase as well as all throughout the project lifecycle and in the aftermath of it is available. This includes the organization of webinars and traditional schools on relevant scientific, technical, managerial and RI-policy topics, in case a critical mass of interested users expresses these training needs.

Messages on these concepts will be appropriately framed according to the diverse target audiences and contexts.

Visual identity

Promoscience has defined a colour palette, a project logo and templates (PowerPoint and Word) to be used by all partners for all communication activities, both internal and external ones. Attention will be paid to use three slightly different logo versions:

1. The NFFA (Nanoscience foundries and fine analysis) logo that represents the research model for advanced nanofabrication and characterization of nanostructures.

2. The NFFA-Europe logo that represents the research infrastructure implementing the NFFA model Europe wide.

3. The NFFA-Europe Pilot logo representing the new project financed by the European Commission, thanks to which the research offer can be delivered free of charge to users whose research plan has been approved.

Key to the success of NFFA-Europe Pilot's visual identity will be the proper use of its visual elements and tools by all partners. Visual identity guidelines will be set up to help them to easily yet effectively promote NFFA-Europe and NFFA-Europe Pilot's image.

The Image User Guide will include information about the logo and its usage, the colour palette, the fonts used and how to correctly acknowledge the support of the European Commission. The guidelines will be published on the project's intranet where partners will be able to download them along with the templates.

Logo & logo usage

The project logo will be an important graphic element and must be used consistently and appropriately. Different versions (colored, black and white) will be available.

Communication standards

Templates complying with the graphical character of the project will be made available to all partners on the project intranet. They will include the following:

- Word templates for all documents produced within the project (e.g. headed letters, reports, press releases, templates for deliverables, others). Using these templates, partners will have full control over the information content while ensuring the coherence of the visuals.
- PowerPoint templates for each single partner. Along with the project logo, they will contain the partner's logo placed on the front page and in the inner pages.

Communication channels and tools

The communication channels identified so far are the following:

- websites (the project's webportal and the partners' websites)
- social media channels
- print and broadcast media
- public events/presentations (organized either by the project partners or others)
- direct emails
- newsletters

Webportal

The **project's webportal** builds on the already existing one of NFFA-Europe (<https://www.nffa.eu/>). It will be restyled, updated and expanded, making visitors aware of the new offer of services.

The webportal is designed so researchers can browse the catalogue of services offered (section: offer) and submit their research proposal directly through the web (section: apply). Furthermore, the webportal hosts a news section (section: news) and editorial work about the project and its ongoing research (section: outcomes). It provides visitors with an interest in the nanosciences and technologies as well as current and potential users, the scientific community and other stakeholders, with a direct and in-depth source of information about the project (section: about and all other sections). It contains articles about various topics related to the nanosciences and technologies, interviews with experts, current and past researchers, and press releases about project highlights.

The webportal will be kept up to date throughout the entire project lifetime by Promoscience and the Project Coordinator. Moreover, in the final period of the project lifetime, when new project results will be available, more material will be added for the purpose of communication and dissemination.

Having links from distinguished websites pointing to www.nffa.eu will be important to improve NFFA's website ranking in SEO (Search Engine Optimization) and ultimately its visibility. In correspondence with important steps of the project, **NFFA-Europe Pilot partners** will be asked to advertise it on their **websites** to raise awareness about the project. This could be done with either a news/highlight box or by putting a banner in a visible part of their website, linking it to www.nffa.eu.

The NFFA website performance will be measured throughout the project lifetime with Google Analytics to obtain the metrics and adapt communication strategies.

If a project partner creates a page dedicated to the project, it must put a visible link or banner pointing to www.nffa.eu and should monitor the visit count to the pages related to the project.

Social Media

Maintaining and expanding our community of interested individuals and groups will be essential in order to achieve our communication objectives. Social networks will play a key role in keeping and enlarging a web community around the project and in making NFFA-Europe Pilot a reference point for news, information and conversations on different topics related to the nanosciences and technologies. The social networks envisaged are Twitter and LinkedIn.

Twitter is an excellent platform that allows us to observe what people think and comment about the nanosciences and other fields related to them. It will be a useful tool to ensure the constant flow of updated information and to let people follow the life of the project and related events in real-time. A Twitter account for the NFFA-Europe Infrastructure has just been created, from where the new services offered thanks to NFFA-Europe Pilot will be promoted. The account will be used to spread information about the project and its achievements, events organised, events in which NFFA-Europe Pilot researchers have participated, as well as about new scientific publications originating from the project. It will furthermore be used to communicate about the publication of new content on the NFFA-Europe website, as well as to monitor and engage relevant stakeholders.

The communication team will start expanding the community by searching for accounts pinpointed in the stakeholder list as followers. All relevant European bodies will be targeted and followed as well. Once the basic community is established and stable, the team will start creating more connections based on similar interests.

An analysis will be carried out to identify a repertoire of unbranded hashtags to attract followers, give tweets more visibility and help reach a wide audience (e.g. #nanosciences, #nanotechnology, #nanomaterials or more general hashtags such as #EUfunded, and others). Reference to relevant external social accounts will be used to issue selected tweets for retweets. We will also retweet relevant posts by scientific journals'/organisations'/other projects' accounts that we will follow. Project partners are expected to help communicate and promote the project and its action lines through their social accounts.

An NFFA-Europe Infrastructure corporate page on **LinkedIn** through which to promote NFFA-Europe Pilot has been created already and currently counts 128 followers. LinkedIn will help establish NFFA-Europe and Pilot as a standout initiative in the field, make its name known and create a network of connections with professional audiences that could be interested in its work and research results. The page will include all relevant and attractive information about the project, its areas of expertise, the professionals it involves and the outputs it will produce.

A **YouTube** channel from where to publish educational and promotional videos about the NFFA-Europe Infrastructure has been established and a **Facebook** account is already active as well.

Social network performance will be measured throughout the project lifetime using Twitter and LinkedIn analytics tools.

NFFA-Europe Pilot partners' websites and social networks list

A list detailing all the partners' websites and social networks is provided below as an example. Through this list, partners get an overview of the different online communication tools used by the consortium members. Members can then choose to share project relevant communication resources on various online tools and retweet or re-post content in order to boost the impact of our communication efforts and strengthen the NFFA-Europe and Pilot community.

Table 1 – NFFA-Europe Pilot partners websites and social networks

Partner	Website	LinkedIn	Twitter	YouTube
1				
2				
3				
...				

Project partners are invited to fill out this list with their team members' websites and social network accounts.

Communication and dissemination materials

Different kinds of documents will be used by the project's partners to promote NFFA-Europe and Pilot. Some of the documents will be produced by using communication standard templates that will be provided, while others will be designed by Promoscience.

Within M06, Promoscience will design and make available a leaflet, a booklet an A1 poster and a roll up of the project to be circulated for project information and promotion. A browsable pdf replicating the project booklet content but optimized for pc reading and desktop printing will be also produced. These materials will be described in Deliverable D17.3.

Other materials could be produced during the project depending on the needs. Possibly a final booklet containing a description of the major project outputs will be produced.

Table 2 - Main components of the NFFA-Europe and Pilot communication and dissemination kit

<i>Material</i>	Poster, roll-up
<i>Purpose</i>	to serve informational and promotional purposes
<i>Format</i>	printed material
<i>Distribution</i>	partners; to be publicly exhibited at partner institutions and project event locations

<i>Material</i>	Brochure
<i>Purpose</i>	to serve informational and promotional purposes
<i>Format</i>	printed material; browsable pdf optimized for pc reading and desktop printing
<i>Distribution</i>	partners; project event participants; stakeholder database. To be available at the partners' premises, and event locations; sent by email and available for download from the project website

<i>Material</i>	Booklet
<i>Purpose</i>	to serve dissemination purposes
<i>Format</i>	printed material; browsable pdf optimized for pc reading and desktop printing
<i>Distribution</i>	partners; events; stakeholder database. To be available at event locations; sent by email and available for download from project website

Media relations, project press releases and journal articles

Press releases for the press and audiovisual media will be published at strategic times, e.g. to announce the first call for proposals, at the kick-off meeting and during the project. As a general rule, Promoscience will produce the project press releases in English and each partner will have them translated in their respective languages. Each partner will share the press releases with their own local media and press offices. If a partner is willing to produce a press release, this will be shared with the coordinator and Promoscience and, once approved, with all the partners.

To optimise the interaction with media professionals, Promoscience will create a press kit, project sheets, and info-graphics to give a quick-to-understand overview of key concepts, interoperability issues, best practices and results.

NFFA-Europe Pilot editorial content will be promoted in a number of networks for science, technology and specialist media. Original journalistic articles profiling the researchers' experience within the project, challenges and key achievements in more detail will be communicated. Anchored on the project website, they will be shared with influential multiplier websites in specialist media, stakeholder networks and established online groups on platforms like LinkedIn.

Table 3 – Communication deliverables for media relations

<i>Material</i>	Press Release
<i>Purpose</i>	to serve informational and promotional purposes
<i>Format</i>	MS-word or pdf files on project templates

<i>Drafted by</i>	PROMOSCIENCE in EN and ITA and then translated by partners into their national languages. Additional press releases by partners.
<i>Distribution</i>	Via partners and partners' press offices; media contacts. To be circulated by email and available for download from the project website.

<i>Material</i>	Project sheets, infographics (X4)
<i>Purpose</i>	Informational
<i>Format</i>	Printed material, browsable pdf optimized for pc reading and desktop printing.
<i>Distribution</i>	Via media contacts. To be circulated by email and available for download from project website

<i>Material</i>	Journalistic articles (X9)
<i>Purpose</i>	Informational
<i>Format</i>	MS-word or pdf files on project templates
<i>Drafted by</i>	PROMOSCIENCE in collaboration with all partners
<i>Distribution</i>	Via specialised media and stakeholder contacts. To be circulated by email and social networks and available for download from project website

Video

Various videos in professional HD broadcast standard have already been produced in the past by Promoscience to describe NFFA-Europe as a distributed infrastructure. Promoscience will update these videos and produce more so as to highlight the new services and the new techniques offered through NFFA-Europe Pilot in the form of knowledge pills, interviews with researchers and success stories. The videos will target in particular potential new researchers and will be shared with all partners and published on the project's website and on social media. Due to the huge success of educational videos produced in the past, explaining various techniques in five-minutes, more of those videos will be made available to potential users and researchers in the near future.

Email contacts

For the purpose of informing about and promoting dissemination events and to engage specific stakeholder groups, direct contacts by email will be used to reach relevant stakeholders. The direct contact will consist of a tailored message and a pdf brochure about the project and the opportunities it provides.

Public Events

If possible, the partners should promote the project at relevant public events (e.g. workshops and conferences organized by the European Materials Research Society, EMRS, as mentioned in the Dissemination Plan; Research Nights; etc.). Participation in public events (at either the local, national or international level) will be advertised on the project website in a dedicated space.

COMMUNICATION REFERENCE TABLE

The communication requirements for NFFA-Europe Pilot are summarized in the table below.

Table 4 – NFFA-Europe Pilot Communication matrix

To be promoted/communicated	Objective of Communication	Audience	Medium	Communication tools to be used	Owner
Project kickoff	Introducing the project team and the project; creating awareness	Academia and Research Community, all stakeholder groups, general public	NFFA website; media relations; partner websites and social networks	Press release; news on websites; posts on social networks; banner	Promoscience; all partners
Project life (meetings; partner participation in external events; partners' achievements; etc)	Creating a continuous flow of updated information about the project; advertising project events or activities	Academia and Research Community, all stakeholder groups, general public,	Website; NFFA social networks	News on the project website; posts on social networks; banners; images	Promoscience; all partners
Project concepts and approaches; expected impact of user results	Creating awareness about the project; promoting its approach; overcoming barriers; supporting the creation of conditions for future uptake of project results	Academia and Research Community, all stakeholder groups, general public	Website; NFFA social networks; media relations	Website section; posts on social networks; brochure; journalistic articles; project sheets; infographics	Promoscience supported by all partners
User engagement activities	Supporting the creation of a community of interested people	Current and potential users	Email/direct contact; website; social networks	Materials (letters, reports, others) drafted using project communication standards; brochure; news on the project website; posts on social networks	Promoscience; all partners
Project related topics	Creating a community of interested people; promoting project concepts and approaches; establishing NFFA as a reference point in the fields of interest	Academia & Research Community, stakeholder groups, general public	Website; media relations; social networks	Journalist articles; website section; posts on social media	Promoscience supported by partner experts

Dissemination events (Workshops, conferences, seminars, training sessions, presentation of highlight proposals)	Advertising project events; encouraging stakeholder participation	Academia and Research Community, Stakeholder groups	Email/direct contact; website; social networks	Announcements and advertisements on project's and partners' websites and social networks; agendas; news on project website and posts on social networks	Promoscience supported by partner experts
Project publications and achievements	Informing on the dissemination of project results	Academia and Research Community, all stakeholder groups, general public	Media relations; website; social networks	Press releases; project sheets and infographics; news on the project website; posts on social networks	Promoscience, all partners

WHO IS IN CHARGE

Partners will identify among their institutes one person who will be in charge of coordinating communication activities at the partner level. The person in charge will be responsible for following the guidelines laid out in this document and coordinate his/her partner activity with Promoscience and the Project Coordinator.

Table 5 - Persons in charge (Example)

Partner	Person in charge of communication	E-mail	Telephone
1			
2			
3			
...			

A number of project ambassadors and spokespersons for communication with specific stakeholder groups will be identified and integrated into this list.

MONITORING COMMUNICATION PERFORMANCE

To maximize communication efforts and evaluate if they are reaching the expected goal, Promoscience will monitor and measure a set of specific indicators including the following:

- N° of press releases produced and circulated;
- N° of copies of brochures disseminated;
- N° of articles/appearances in press and media;
- N° of visits per month on the project website;
- N° of news articles published per month on the project website;
- N° of posts published per month on social networks;
- N° of messages sent to the project mail address;
- N° of views of videos published on YouTube
- N° of downloads of documents from the project website.

Twitter, LinkedIn and Google Analytics will be used to monitor project social networks and website performance and draft reports on their performance.

Promoscience has developed a monitoring tool that will be filled in periodically throughout the project lifetime and at each reporting period. Promoscience will be responsible for collecting data and partners' inputs and producing aggregated tables. The monitoring tool consists of a set of template tables where details about the communication actions performed will be specified. The Excel monitoring tool is attached to this plan as Annex II.

ANNEXES

Annex I – Format to collect stakeholder data

Organisation name	Organisation description	Organisation address	Main contact person	Telephone/mobile number	e-mail address	Skype name	Website	LinkedIn	Twitter
A1	B1	C1	D1	E1	F1	G1	H1	I1	J1
A2	B2	C2	D2	E2	F2	G2	H2	I2	J2

Annex II – Monitoring tool

1. EVENT PARTICIPATED									
Partner	Event title	Type of event	Date & place	Type of audience	Number of participants	Type of contribution given	Link to program	Link to ppt/material presented	Notes
A1	B1	C1	D1	E1	F1	G1	H1	I1	J1
A2	B2	C2	D2	E2	F2	G2	H2	I2	J2

2. EVENTS ORGANIZED BY PARTNERS							
Partner	Event title	Type of event	Date & place	Type of audience	Topic/purpose of the event	Number of participants	
A1	B1	C1	D1	E1	F1	G1	
A2	B2	C2	D2	E2	F2	G2	

Level of involvement and satisfaction of participants	Link to program	Link to ppt/material presented	Link to video	Notes
H1	I1	J1	K1	L1
H2	I2	J2	K2	L2

3. PRESS RELEASES			
Partner	Link to press release	Recipient's (media or others) name	Recipient's (media or others) contact

A1	B1	C1	D1
A2	B2	C2	D2

4. ARTICLES/APPEARANCE IN PRESS AND MEDIA				
Journal/press/broadcast media	Focus	Link to press review or others	Type of audience	Contact
A1	B1	C1	D1	E1
A2	B2	C2	D2	E2

5. DISSEMINATED BROCHURES						
Partner	Dissemination channel	Date&place	Recipient's name (organization or others)	Recipient's contacts (organization or others)	Recipient's LinkedIn account (organization or others)	Recipient's Twitter account (organization or others)
A1	B1	C1	D1	E1	F1	G1
A2	B2	C2	D2	E2	F2	G2

